

ability we reproduce the corrected equations for σ_1 and σ_2 .

$$\sigma_1 = \left[\frac{\Delta P}{\Delta \pi_1} \right]_{J_v=0, \Delta \pi_2=0}$$

$$= - \frac{\left[\frac{(\bar{V}_s)_1}{(\bar{C}_s)_1} \frac{\partial(J_s)_1}{\partial(\Delta \mu_s)_1} + \frac{(\bar{V}_s)_2}{(\bar{C}_s)_1} \frac{\partial(J_s)_2}{\partial(\Delta \mu_s)_1} + \frac{\bar{V}_w}{(\bar{C}_s)_1} \frac{\partial J_w}{\partial(\Delta \mu_s)_1} - (\bar{V}_s)_1 \bar{V}_w \frac{\partial(J_s)_1}{\partial \Delta \mu_w} - \bar{V}_w (\bar{V}_s)_2 \frac{\partial(J_s)_2}{\partial \Delta \mu_w} - \bar{V}_w^2 \frac{\partial J_w}{\partial \Delta \mu_w} \right]}{\left[(\bar{V}_s)_1^2 \frac{\partial(J_s)_1}{\partial(\Delta \mu_s)_1} + (\bar{V}_s)_2 (\bar{V}_s)_1 \frac{\partial(J_s)_2}{\partial(\Delta \mu_s)_1} + \bar{V}_w (\bar{V}_s)_1 \frac{\partial J_w}{\partial(\Delta \mu_s)_1} + (\bar{V}_s)_1 (\bar{V}_s)_2 \frac{\partial(J_s)_1}{\partial(\Delta \mu_s)_2} + (\bar{V}_s)_2^2 \frac{\partial(J_s)_2}{\partial(\Delta \mu_s)_2} \right.}$$

$$\left. + (\bar{V}_w (\bar{V}_s)_2 \frac{\partial J_w}{\partial(\Delta \mu_s)_2} + (\bar{V}_s)_1 \bar{V}_w \frac{\partial(J_s)_1}{\partial \Delta \mu_w} + (\bar{V}_s)_2 \bar{V}_w \frac{\partial(J_s)_2}{\partial \Delta \mu_w} + \bar{V}_w^2 \frac{\partial J_w}{\partial \Delta \mu_w} \right]} \dots (4)$$

and

$$\sigma_2 = \left[\frac{\Delta P}{\Delta \pi_2} \right]_{J_v=0, \Delta \pi_1=0}$$

$$= - \frac{\left[\frac{(\bar{V}_s)_1}{(\bar{C}_s)_2} \frac{\partial(J_s)_1}{\partial(\Delta \mu_s)_2} + \frac{(\bar{V}_s)_2}{(\bar{C}_s)_2} \frac{\partial(J_s)_2}{\partial(\Delta \mu_s)_2} + \frac{\bar{V}_w}{(\bar{C}_s)_2} \frac{\partial J_w}{\partial(\Delta \mu_s)_2} - \bar{V}_w (\bar{V}_s)_1 \frac{\partial(J_s)_1}{\partial \Delta \mu_w} - \bar{V}_w (\bar{V}_s)_2 \frac{\partial(J_s)_2}{\partial \Delta \mu_w} - \bar{V}_w^2 \frac{\partial J_w}{\partial \Delta \mu_w} \right]}{\left[(\bar{V}_s)_1^2 \frac{\partial(J_s)_1}{\partial(\Delta \mu_s)_1} + (\bar{V}_s)_2 (\bar{V}_s)_1 \frac{\partial(J_s)_2}{\partial(\Delta \mu_s)_1} + (\bar{V}_s)_1 \bar{V}_w \frac{\partial J_w}{\partial(\Delta \mu_s)_1} + (\bar{V}_s)_1 (\bar{V}_s)_2 \frac{\partial(J_s)_1}{\partial(\Delta \mu_s)_2} + (\bar{V}_s)_2^2 \frac{\partial(J_s)_2}{\partial(\Delta \mu_s)_2} \right.}$$

$$\left. + \bar{V}_w (\bar{V}_s)_2 \frac{\partial J_w}{\partial(\Delta \mu_s)_2} + (\bar{V}_s)_1 \bar{V}_w \frac{\partial(J_s)_1}{\partial \Delta \mu_w} + (\bar{V}_s)_2 \bar{V}_w \frac{\partial(J_s)_2}{\partial \Delta \mu_w} + \bar{V}_w^2 \frac{\partial J_w}{\partial \Delta \mu_w} \right]} \dots (5)$$

They are found to be, separately, equal to unity without taking recourse to $\Delta C_1 = \Delta C_2 = \Delta C/2$, i.e., without the application of the specific rider used by the authors¹. It can be emphasised, therefore, that the reflection coefficient of a membrane remains unaffected from the concentrations of the different individual components of the system so long as the solution preserves its dilute nature. The result, thus obtained, in the above generalised manner, also embodies the findings of the authors¹ whose case refers to only one particular situation. This is also in conformity with equation (16) (Ref.1) of the authors⁵. Thus for the condition $\sigma_1 = 1$ and $\sigma_2 = 1$ equation (16) (Ref. 1) is written as

$$\sigma \Delta C = \Delta C_1 + \Delta C_2 = \Delta C$$

so that

$$\sigma = 1$$

It has to be noted that for σ to be unity the condition $(J_s)_1 = (J_s)_2 = 0$ has to be satisfied for either conditions, i.e., whether we deal with the interacting situation or the non-interacting situation, as mentioned by the authors¹.

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Effect of Third Component on the Phase Separation of Triethylamine and Water System—A Comparative Study

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THE effect of 1 : 1 electrolytes on the phase separation temperature (PST) of a solvent mixture of 40% by weight of triethylamine (TEA) in water is studied, using data from literature¹⁻¹⁶, along with a number of new measurements of the PST using standard procedures¹⁷.

Results and Discussion

Effect of Anion: Table 1 shows the effects of alkali metal and ammonium halides on the PST of TEA—Water mixture. It is seen that the smaller anions (Chloride and Bromide) give negative ΔT , where ΔT is the PST of the ternary mixture minus the PST of the binary solvent mixture. The bigger

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF ALKALI AND AMMONIUM SALTS ON PST OF TEA-WATER MIXTURE OF COMPOSITION 40% BY WEIGHT OF TEA†

Anion \ Cation	Cl ⁻ (1.81)	Br ⁻ (1.96)	I ⁻ (2.19)	OH ⁻ (1.40)	CH ₃ COO ⁻ (1.59)	NO ₃ ⁻ (1.89)	CNS ⁻ (1.95)	ClO ₄ ⁻ (2.36)
Li ⁺ (0.68)	-	-	+	-	-	-	+	+
Na ⁺ (0.95)	-	-	+	-	-	-*	+	+
K ⁺ (1.33)	-	-	+	-	-	-*	+	+
Rb ⁺ (1.48)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
NH ₄ ⁺ (1.50)	-	-	+	-*	-	-	+	-
Ca ⁺ (1.69)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

+...ΔT is positive (salting-in effect);
 -...ΔT is negative (salting-out effect);
 Ion radii are given in parenthesis in angstrom unit.

† References 1-16.
 * Present studies.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF 1 : 1 ELECTROLYTES ON PST OF TEA-WATER MIXTURE OF COMPOSITION 40% BY WEIGHT OF TEA

Anion \ Cation	Hydroxide	Formate	Acetate	Chloride	Chloroacetate	Bromide	Nitrate	Trichloroacetate	Iodide	Thiocyanate	Perchlorate	Benzoate	Picrate	Octanesulphonate	Decanesulphonate	Undecane-sulphonate	Laurate	Myristate	Palmitate	Hydnocarpate	Elaidate	Stearate	
H ⁺	-	-	-	-*	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Li ⁺	-*	-	-	-	-*	-	-*	-*	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Na ⁺	-	-	-	-	-	-	-*	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
K ⁺	-	-	-	-	-	-	-*	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Rb ⁺	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
NH ₄ ⁺	-*	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Ca ⁺	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Me ₄ N ⁺	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Et ₃ NH ⁺	-*	-*	-*	-*	-*	-*	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Et ₃ N	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
DTEA	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
DPy	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
HDTEA	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

+...ΔT is positive (salting-in effect);
 -...ΔT is negative (salting-out effect);

* Present studies. DTEA—Dodecyltriethylammonium ion;
 DPy—Dodecylpyridinium ion and
 HDTEA—Hexadecyltriethylammonium ion.

anion (Iodide) gives positive ΔT. Thus an anion-size effect on the PST is revealed. The behaviour of the complex anions, hydroxide, acetate, nitrate, thiocyanate and perchlorate (their sizes are from thermochemical data^{1,9}) only confirms this effect.

Effect of Cation: All the data are collected together in Table 2. Smaller anions (e.g. Bromide) producing negative ΔT in combination with small

cations (e.g. alkali metal ions) produce positive ΔT when combined with larger cations (like dodecyltriethylammonium ion). These results indicate that ultimately the combined size of anion and cation decides the sign of ΔT although the contribution from anion size is greater than that from cation size.

Effect of Acids: The cation H⁺ combined with trichloroacetate or nitrate anion gives positive

ΔT , contrary to expectation (Table 2). This may be because when these acids are added to the basic TEA-Water mixture, it is the salt produced, triethylammonium trichloroacetate or triethylammonium nitrate, which decides the sign of ΔT .

Thus the present study reveals a systematic effect of ion-size on the PST of the TEA-Water system. Electrolytes of smaller ions give negative ΔT , while larger ions give positive ΔT . This size effect may be referred to making or breaking of structure in water¹⁹⁻²¹, which in turn results in negative or positive ΔT , as per the ionic sizes.

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Synthesis and Study of Anthelmintic Activity of Some Newer Benzimidazoles

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COMPOUNDS containing benzimidazole nucleus have been reported to possess a wide spectrum of anthelmintic activity. Several benzimidazole derivatives e.g., thiabendazole, mebendazole, flubendazole etc are used clinically¹ for the eradication of helminthic infections. The incorporation of substituted isothiocyanates in benzimidazole nucleus results in an increase in the anthelmintic activity². In continuation of our interest on the search of new anthelmintic compounds, we have synthesized benzimidazolyl thiosemicarbazides and screened them for their anthelmintic activity against *H. nana*.

Experimental

All the compounds were routinely checked by tlc on Silica Gel 'G' using benzene/methanol as solvent system, ir spectrum of compounds 9 and 19 was determined using a Perkin-Elmer Model 137. The melting points were taken in open capillary and are uncorrected.

1. *2-Benzimidazole acetic acid hydrazide*: It was prepared from ethyl 2-benzimidazole acetate following the method of Ralph³ et al.

2. *1-N-2-(2'-acetobenzimidazolyl)-4-aryl thiosemicarbazides*: 2-Benzimidazolyl acetic acid hydrazide (0.01 mole) was taken in dry benzene and appropriate substituted phenyl isothiocyanate (0.01 mole) was added to it. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 4 hrs; on cooling a crystalline solid separated out, it was filtered and washed with petroleum ether to remove excess of isothiocyanate and recrystallized from ethanol (50%). Details of the compounds are listed in Table 1.

Compound 9 showed characteristic bands for C=O (1660 cm⁻¹) C=N (1610 cm⁻¹) and C=S (1050 cm⁻¹) in the ir spectrum.

3. *1-N-2-(2'-ethyl benzimidazolyl)-4-aryl thiosemicarbazides*: 1-N-(2-acetobenzimidazolyl)-4-aryl thiosemicarbazide (1 mole) was suspended in dry ether (100 ml), to this solution LAH (2 mole) was added slowly in 30 minutes and left overnight. The unreacted LAH was decomposed, filtered and usual

* Part of this work will be incorporated in the Ph.D. Thesis of (Miss) Garima Sathi.

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